

Original article

Assessment of Gamma Dose Rate in Outdoor Environments in Selected Locations of Awjila and Jalu, Southeast Libya

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ABSTRACT

Aims. The primary objective of this study was to estimate the absorbed dose rate of the naturally occurring radioactive nuclides at a height of one meter above earth's surface. **Methods.** The outdoor radiation exposure dose rates caused by radioactivity concentrations of radionuclides in the soil have been evaluated at several locations in Awjilah and Jalu, Libya, using portable devices RADEX RD 1501 and LB 123. **Results.** Thirty-seven random sites were examined. The absorbed dosage rate ranged from 34.8357 to 95.7734 nGy/hr in dry air at a height of one meter above the ground, with 77.579 nGy/hr being the average. The calculated average annual outdoor effective dose equivalents are 0.0951 mSv/y. **Conclusion.** The current data could represent the baseline values of natural radioactivity in the research area since no extreme value was discovered at any of the surveyed sites.

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INTRODUCTION

Our planet has been regarded as radioactive since it was created. Ionizing radiation exists and exposes us to energetic electromagnetic waves and radiation in the form of particles and waves. These ionizing radiations can destroy the bonds between atoms and electrons without the use of heat by ejecting one or more electrons from their orbit [1]. One of the main sources of ionizing radiation is the radioactivity of some naturally occurring radionuclides in rocks and soils, which include traces of the Uranium (238U) and Thorium (232Th) series as well as radioactive Potassium (40K). These naturally occurring radioactive elements significantly contribute to the annual gross dose that we receive. In fact, the majority of human exposure to energetic radiation is due to cosmic and terrestrial radiation [2]. In the absence of a comprehensive study that answers the posed question; what would be the background radiation dose rate in the region of interest (Awjilah and Jalu)? This study will be considered a base study to follow any future changes in the background. Since the majority of building materials come from the crust of the earth, it seems sense that indoor gamma radiation exposure would be higher than outdoor gamma radiation exposure. Most people only spend 20% of their time outside and more than 80% of their time indoors [3, 4].

According to a number of international studies on the population's effective dosage, outdoor exposure has a global dose rate value of 59 mSv/h (with a range of 18 to 93 nSv/h) [2,7]. In general, only around 1.2 percent of the country (Libya) is cultivated; the other 95% is wilderness or desert [8]. Libya's two major soil classes are yermosols and xerosols. Soils in the country are typically superficial, sandy in texture, poor in organic matter, and low in water-holding capacity [9]. In this current work, Awjilah and Jalu Oases have been selected as the regions of interest. They are two of the three towns in the desert, south of Ajdabiya [10]. Nearly 150 kilometers south of Benghazi is a town called Ajdabiya, which is also the biggest city in the Al Wahat district. The oases are distinguished by a small hill covered in date palm trees and surrounded by a sand plain.

In this study, our ultimate aim is to estimate the absorbed dose rates in the air at a one-meter height above the ground. It is important to highlight that, despite our diligent search, we were unable to locate any studies that considered radiation exposure in relation to the study region (Al Wahat, Awjilah, and Jalu). In reality, there is little information available about

gamma dosage rates indoors and outdoors in the majority of Libyan districts. In order to compare any anticipated change in the background radiation of a particular district with tabulated data, a base study must be established because the levels of background radiation in a territory are impacted by man-made nuclear operations and accidents [5,6]. In other words, we are estimating the annual effective dosage of people in these locations with its associated outdoor exposure, as well as to determine the present background radiation in the aforementioned region (the province of Al Wahat).

METHODS

Study design and setting

As shown in Figure 1, thirty-seven randomly selected locations in Awjilah and Jalu were chosen to estimate the gamma dose rate outdoors. Awjilah's city center is considered the reference point for all the sites. Each place has been given a number. The designated numbers run from L1 to L37. Table 1 lists the location distance from the reference point (Awjilah city center), the position GPS coordinates (latitude and longitude in degrees), and some remarkable notes. The table clearly shows that L15, which is around 26.4 kilometers to the west of Awjilah's town center, is the place that is the furthest away. The measurement locations within the boundaries of Jalu are sites L1 through L10. The radiation absorbed dose level in the abovementioned locations is measured by means of RADEX RD 1501 and LB 123 portable instruments. Each site has been investigated by the two devices at one meter above the ground (a well-designed stand was utilized to guarantee a fixed distance from the ground); 5 minutes was satisfactory for the stability of measurement. Two readings were tallied at each site for exact measurement reasons for each of the 37 locations, and the mean values were computed.

Figure 1. The investigated sites in Awjilah and Jalu.

Data collection procedure

The relationship between the absorbed dose rate in dry air ($D_{dry-air}$) and the exposure dose rate (E) is expressed as [11]

$$D_{dry-air} \left(\frac{mSv}{hr} \right) = 0.0087 \times E \left(\frac{R}{hr} \right) \quad (1)$$

with 0.0087 being the conversion factor for one Roentgen (a unit of ionizing radiation dose) exposure, its unit is GyR. When calculating the outdoor absorbed dose, it is customary to use a 20% occupancy factor. On the other hand, the equivalent dose is taken into account while estimating the annual effective dose. Moreover, it is essential to emphasize here that the decay rate varies delicately with time. As a consequence, ten minutes of total exposure time were considered in each measurement [12]. The effect of ionizing radiation on the human body is very important and should be instituted here. The annual effective dose at each site was estimated with the aid of the formula below.

$$AED_{outdoor} \left(\frac{mSv}{y} \right) = D_{dry-air} \times T \times OF \times \xi \times 10^3 \quad (2)$$

Here, T is a time conversion factor (8760 hr/y), the occupancy factor is denoted by; this is the percentage of time occupancies spent outdoors, which is assumed to be 20% (it is 80% indoors), ξ and is another conversion coefficient that converts the absorbed dose to its counterpart effective dose.

Table 1. Characteristics of the measurement sites in Awjilah and Jalu.

Serial Number	Distance from the Central Point (km)	Coordinates (Degree)		Awjilah/Jalu	Remarks
		Latitude	Longitude		
L1	12.0	29.08737	21.45571	Awjilah	Version land
L2	18.0	29.04416	21.49006	Jalu	Within the city
L3	19.7	29.03760	21.52028	Jalu	Within the city
L4	16.7	29.03215	21.50655	Jalu	Within the city
L5	19.7	29.02495	21.52578	Jalu	Within the city
L6	18.6	29.02375	21.50380	Jalu	Within the city
L7	21.6	29.01174	21.53128	Jalu	Within the city
L8	22.2	29.00814	21.52303	Jalu	Within the city
L9	19.7	29.00117	21.49281	Jalu	Within the city
L10	15.4	29.04776	21.47495	Jalu	Within the city
L11	16.6	29.12337	21.16445	Awjilah	Version land
L12	14.3	29.07537	21.19330	Awjilah	Version land
L13	22.2	29.15575	21.11225	Awjilah	Version land
L14	25.2	29.08497	21.07790	Awjilah	Version land
L15	26.4	29.04656	21.07378	Awjilah	Version land
L16	19.9	29.14736	21.13423	Awjilah	Version land
L17	15.1	29.19532	21.21666	Awjilah	Version land
L18	7.00	29.16295	21.30734	Awjilah	Within the city
L19	10.2	29.14136	21.23867	Awjilah	Agriculture
L20	5.40	29.12817	21.28398	Awjilah	Agriculture
L21	4.20	29.14496	21.31008	Awjilah	Agriculture
L22	3.40	29.14016	21.31558	Awjilah	Within the city
L23	4.10	29.12457	21.29497	Awjilah	Within the city
L24	3.90	29.11737	21.29497	Awjilah	Agriculture
L25	7.90	29.18453	21.31970	Awjilah	Within the city
L26	8.20	29.18693	21.34718	Awjilah	Version land
L27	10.0	29.14496	21.42824	Awjilah	Version land
L28	16.6	29.22649	21.43923	Awjilah	Version land
L29	16.7	29.21450	21.45571	Awjilah	Version land
L30	14.3	29.20012	21.43785	Awjilah	Version land
L31	10.8	29.18094	21.40763	Awjilah	Version land
L32	7.00	29.16895	21.35542	Awjilah	Version land
L33	6.30	29.16175	21.35542	Awjilah	Agriculture
L34	11.3	29.20851	21.31558	Awjilah	Agriculture
L35	6.90	29.17014	21.32245	Awjilah	Version land
L36	3.90	29.13656	21.35679	Awjilah	Version land
L37	5.90	29.08617	21.38977	Awjilah	Agriculture

RESULTS

The measurement results for effective doses (mSv/y) and outdoor absorbed dose rates (nGy/hr) are tabulated in Table 2 with four accuracy digits after the decimal point. Histograms (Figure. 2) show how the absorbed dosages are distributed. The results revealed that the maximum and minimum outdoor dose rates were, respectively, 34.8357 nGy/hr and 95.7734 nGy/hr at location L15, a virgin land 26.4 km from the center of Awjilah. The average outdoor dose rate was determined to be 78.3059 nGy/hr. Table 3 clearly shows that the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles are 69.5722, 78.3059, and 95.7734 nGy/hr, respectively; the first, second, and third quartiles are ranked 8, 19, and 28. For instance, 50% of the absorbed dose rates in dry air are lower than the values at locations L11, L17, L22, L28, L30, or L35. Principally, Figure 2 shows that eight locations are characterized by the largest measure of the outdoor dry-air absorbed dose rate. They are: L5, L6, L18, L19, L21, 26, L27, and L34. In general, the outdoor absorbed dose values are systematic, free of anomalies, and within the global average limit.

Table 2. Outdoor gamma exposure (nGy/hr) and annual effective dose (mSv/y) for selected locations in Awjilah and jalu.

Sample Location	Absorbed Dose Rate Outdoor (nGy/hr)	Annual Effective Dose Outdoor (mSv/y)	Sample Location	Absorbed Dose Rate Outdoor (nGy/hr)	Annual Effective Dose Outdoor (mSv/y)
L1	78.2067	0.0959	L20	87.0397	0.1067
L2	78.3059	0.0960	L21	95.6742	0.1173
L3	43.4702	0.0533	L22	69.5722	0.0853
L4	43.4702	0.0533	L23	78.2067	0.0959
L5	95.6742	0.1173	L24	78.2067	0.0959
L6	95.7734	0.1175	L25	78.2067	0.0959
L7	78.3059	0.0960	L26	95.6742	0.1173
L8	87.0397	0.1067	L27	95.6742	0.1173
L9	87.0397	0.1067	L28	69.5722	0.0853
L10	87.0397	0.1067	L29	87.0397	0.1067
L11	69.5722	0.0853	L30	69.5722	0.0853
L12	78.2067	0.0959	L31	69.5722	0.0853
L13	43.4702	0.0533	L32	87.0397	0.1067
L14	78.3059	0.0960	L33	87.0397	0.1067
L15	34.8357	0.0427	L34	95.6742	0.1173
L16	52.2039	0.0640	L35	69.5722	0.0853
L17	69.5722	0.0853	L36	87.0397	0.1067
L18	95.6742	0.1173	L37	78.2067	0.0959
L19	95.6742	0.1173			

Table 3. Some statistical values for outdoor gamma absorbed dose and annual effective dose for the selected locations.

	$D_{dry-air}$ (nGy/hr)	$AED_{outdoor}$ (mSv/y)
Average	77.5790	0.0951
SD	16.2356	0.0202
Minimum	34.8357	0.0427
25th percentile	69.5722	0.0853
Median	78.3059	0.0960
50th percentile	78.3059	0.0960
75th percentile	87.0397	0.1067
Maximum	95.7734	0.1175

The first quartile is of rank 8, which is commensurate with the measure of location L11, L17, L22, L28, L30, or L35. The second quartile is of rank 19, which corresponds to the measure of location L2, L7, or L14. The third quartile is of rank 28, which corresponds to the measure of location L8-L10, L20, L29, L32, L33, or L36.

Figure 2. The absorbed dose rate in dry air for the measured locations in both Awjilah and Jalu.

The annual effective dosage for the general population was computed in mSv/y and depicted in Figure 3 by means of equation (2). Any attentive eye may quickly discern that none of the areas under examination has a value greater than 1 mSv/y. Consequently, one may say that the natural background radiation in the examined area is not categorized as a high-dose area with respect to the measured absorbed dose rate and the associated annual effective dose rate. The comparison of the annual effective doses (outdoor) for each of the locations that interest us is shown in Figure 3. The maximum value of the outdoor annual effective dose was recorded at location L6, which is within Jalu City, 18.6 km from the reference point. Overall, the investigated locations can be grouped according to the annual effective dose, ascendingly, into five groups, as depicted in Figure 3. It is evident that the values are systematic, with no abrupt increase or drop.

Figure 3. The outdoor annual effective doses of the examined locations in the Oases of Awjilah and Jalu.

DISCUSSION

Thirty-seven random locations in Awjilah and Jalu, southeast of Libya, were selected randomly to estimate the absorbed dose rate of the natural background radiation. All of the locations are within a 26.4 km radius circle. Its origin is in the center of Awjilah city. We have seen that the absorbed dose rates at one meter from the ground in dry have an average value of 77.5790 nGy/hr. Results have also shown that Awjilah and Jalu cities are normal background areas of the country. The average annual outdoor effective dose equivalent for Awjilah and Jalu has been estimated to be 0.0951 mSv/y, which is, much less than 1 mSv/y. On the other hand, the values reported for some other locations are provided to contextualize the findings of this study. In particular, in Iraq, the outdoor gamma dose rate ranged from 565.5 to 1070.1 nGy/h, which is much higher than the values reported in this study. In the same context, the associated annual outdoor effective dose equivalent is 990 μ Sv/y [14]. The outdoor gamma radiation rate of the region around Istanbul was researched by Karahan and Bayulken in 2000; the results of this study are equivalent to those of Istanbul. They discovered that the average yearly outdoor effective dosage equivalent is just 80 μ Sv/y, while the average outdoor gamma dose rate is 65 nGy/y [15]. Nigeria's average yearly

effective dosage equivalent is 98 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, which, with a difference of just 2.9 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$, is comparable to the results of the current study (95.1 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$) [13].

CONCLUSION

For all practical purposes, the values obtained in this study for the cities can be taken to represent the baseline of natural radioactivity, which can be utilized as a yardstick for evaluating the extent of any pollution in the environment due to any accidental releases of radionuclides.

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published, and is not part of a thesis project.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

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